

MICROPINNED JOINTS UNDER LAP SHEAR LOADING CONDITIONS

S. B. Inverarity¹, R. Das², and A. P. Mouritz³

¹ARC Training Centre in Lightweight Automotive Structures, School of Engineering, RMIT University, 124 La Trobe Street, Melbourne, Victoria 3000, Australia, simon.inverarity@student.rmit.edu.au, <https://atlas-innovation.com.au/>

²ARC Training Centre in Lightweight Automotive Structures, School of Engineering, RMIT University, 124 La Trobe Street, Melbourne, Victoria 3000, Australia, raj.das@rmit.edu.au, <https://atlas-innovation.com.au/>

³ARC Training Centre in Lightweight Automotive Structures, School of Engineering, RMIT University, 124 La Trobe Street, Melbourne, Victoria 3000, Australia, adrian.mouritz@rmit.edu.au, <https://atlas-innovation.com.au/>

Keywords: Joining, Micropins, Finite element analysis, Lap shear joints, Micropins

ABSTRACT

Composites and lightweight metals are finding a variety of applications in automotive, aerospace and other sectors due to their high strength and stiffness to weight ratios. Despite the potential of these materials, joining remains an issue limiting their penetration into new markets. Research has suggested an array of interference fit micropins as a potential joining solution for composite to lightweight metal joints. We present a new approach to micropinned joints which involves interference fitting, and its effect is characterised for a composite-to-metal joint under lap shear loading. The tested joints comprised of aluminium alloys and carbon fibre reinforced polymer laminates bridged by steel pins.

Micropinned joints bridged by a single pin were manufactured to attain an understanding of the response to lap shear loading. These joints showed an elastic-plastic response with ultimate load occurring when the pin was partially pulled-out. The ultimate load occurring after pull-out has begun suggests that snubbing and strain hardening of the pin have some effect on the response of the joint. Finite element analysis was able to model this response, supporting the theory of snubbing and strain hardening, adding plasticity to the joint.

A square array of nine micropins was then used to manufacture micropin joints. These joints also showed an elastic-plastic response to lap shear loading with the ultimate load occurring once the pins were partially pulled-out. The total load carried by the nine pins in the square array was more than nine times the load held by one pin. The ultimate bearing stress and yield stress also increased. These results show that interference fit micropins present a potential solution for metal-to-composite joining due to the elastic-plastic response to loading.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composites and lightweight metals are finding a variety of applications in automotive, aerospace and other sectors due to their high strength and stiffness to weight ratios. Despite their potential, joining remains an issue limiting their penetration into new markets [1]. Adhesives and mechanical fasteners are the most common method for producing composite-to-metal joints [2]. Both of these methods have inherent problems. Mechanical fasteners require drilling a hole with a high tolerance, which is expensive and creates a geometric stress raiser. Adhesives are susceptible to catastrophic failure and can be weaker than designed if specific environmental factors are not attained during the application, curing, and service [3]. This research seeks to overcome the problems of these two techniques. Inserting through-thickness, small diameter pins, otherwise known as z-pins, has been shown to improve the fracture toughness of adhesively bonded or co-cured composite-to-composite

joints. An array of z-pins can be used to bridge a mixed material joint with a pre-cured composite [4]. Interference fit micropinning is a variation on z-pinning suited to use with post-cured composites and mixed material joints.

Researchers have investigated interference fit pins and bolts for joining cured composites. Generally, these authors have investigated pins greater than 5 mm in diameter. The interference fit % ($I\%$) can be defined by:

$$I\% = \frac{(D - d)}{d} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where d is the drilled hole diameter and D is the diameter of the pin. The insertion process and lap shear strength have been investigated experimentally and numerically [5-12]. The amount of interference is critical for determining the strength of the joint. A balance should be obtained between too little interference causing negligible surface traction and too much interference causing damage [12]. Some authors suggest interference up to around 2% [10]. For carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) laminates, the maximum interference before damage occurs decreases with increasing pin diameter, and for a 4 mm diameter pin should be 1.1% [9].

Analytical models, experimental tests and numerical models have all been used to investigate the lap shear response of interference fit pins and bolts. Analytical models have been developed to evaluate the bearing strength of an interference pin joint [13], a multiple pin joint [13], and the residual stresses around the hole [8]. Experimental tests and numerical models have been developed to investigate the lap shear response of interference fit pins and bolts. Tests with glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP) laminate have shown an improvement in bearing stiffness and reductions in the radial and tangential strains compared to transition fit pinned joints [7]. Modelling the insertion and bearing failure mode of the composite requires the use of progressive failure models. Several researchers [12, 14, 15] suggest methods for implementing progressive composite failure in interference fit joints.

Interference fits improve the fatigue life of joints compared to transition and clearance fit fasteners. Kim et al. [11] found a 1% interference fit in GFRP increased the fatigue life six times compared to a transition fit. The improvement is due to a reduction in the hoop stress around the hole, a more uniform distribution of residual stress, and a reduction in the magnitude of local oscillatory stresses [10].

Z-pins are a method of increasing the interlaminar fracture toughness of composites and increasing the ultimate strength and peel resistance to composite-to-composite joints. Z-pinning involves inserting small diameter (generally <1 mm) pins through-the-thickness of composite materials before curing. The z-pins transfer load between delaminated plies of the composite or across a fractured joint. Mouritz [16] presents a review into z-pinned composites and their joints. The mechanical properties of z-pinned joints have been analysed analytically, producing a constitutive model [17-19]. A Matlab addition to ANSYS implemented this constitutive model for finite element models of a pin-reinforced joint [20].

Experimental tests on z-pin reinforced T-joints have shown that z-pins improve the fatigue resistance, toughness and peel resistance of the joint compared to co-curing alone [21-25]. These effects are due to the z-pins change the mode of failure for the sample [26]. Mode II delamination tests have shown that if the joint fails through the pins pulling out, there is an improvement in the toughness and displacement to failure with the joint exhibiting a non-linear plastic response [27]. If the pins fail by shear rather than pull out, this plastic response is not observed [28]. Lap shear loading leads to secondary bending, and a mixed-mode failure [22].

Z-pins have been used to reinforce metal-to-composite joints. Cylindrical and ball-tip pins have been added to the surface of metal substrates using cold metal fusion [29]. The addition of the pins has improved the ultimate tensile strength and elongation to failure compared to co-curing alone. Selective

Laser Melting (SLM) has been used to manufacture pins on the surface of metal substrates. The surface roughness inherent in SLM manufacturing improved the mode I fracture toughness of the composite-to-metal interface [30]. These pins were able to support lap shear load, also improving the toughness compared to co-curing alone [4]. This work seeks to combine ideas from both interference fit pin joints and z-pins. The interference fit pin produces a geometric stress raiser due to the hole. Using an array of small diameter z-pins reduces this effect by reducing the hole size. Z-pins, however, are generally inserted into the pre-cured composite and rely on adhesion to the composite matrix and fibre tension to provide surface traction. This work will instead use the interference fit in a post-cured composite to provide the surface traction.

This paper presents the development and characterisation of micropinned joints between aluminium alloy and CFRP laminate substrates bridged using steel micropins under the lap shear loading condition. The load for inserting a single pin was measured. The single pin joint was loaded to failure under lap shear conditions. A numerical model of a single pin joint investigated the phenomena during loading. Tests then investigated the response of multi-pin joints under lap-shear loading. The results were compared to an equivalent numerical model.

2 METHODOLOGY

A series of experimental tests and numerical simulations were carried out to characterise the structural properties and failure mode of an interference fit micropinned lap shear joint. Lap shear test coupons were manufactured with dimensions as per ASTM D5961 [31]. The CFRP sheet was four-ply $[90,0]_s$ T700/VTM264 with a total thickness of 0.88 mm. The aluminium sheet was 2 mm thick and made of AA 6061-T6. Micropins were nominally 0.5 mm diameter steel rods with a tapered point. The average diameter was measured under a microscope to be 0.505 mm. Each aluminium-to-CFRP joint had 0.500 mm holes drilled into the overlap region using a CNC machine. The entire length of the tapered micropin was pulled through the hole. The pin was cut as close as possible to the surface of the joint and finally ground and polished to be flush with the surface of the substrate. Figure 1 shows a steel pin before insertion.

Figure 1: Pin before insertion

3 MODEL OF DECREASE IN LOAD DUE TO SMEARING

Numerical models were used to identify the change in stress for an array of micropins compared to a single fastener. These models investigated the effect on both the aluminium sheet and the CFRP sheet with and without the interference fit steel pin. The modeling was carried out Abaqus 6.14. A 3D implicit analysis was carried out by applying a 0.1mm displacement to the substrate and measuring the change in the peak stress. The modeling used 56576 hexahedral solid elements with reduced

integration (C3D8R) for the aluminum sheet with multiple holes, and each of the four plies of the CFRP sheet with multiple holes had 12812 hexahedral solid elements with reduced integration (C3D8R). The micropins were meshed with 1140 hexahedral solid elements with reduced integration (C3D8R). The single hole aluminium sheet and each ply of the single hole CFRP sheet were meshed with 19328 and 2807 hexahedral solid elements with reduced integration (C3D8R) respectively. The single fastener was meshed with 2484 hexahedral solid elements with reduced integration (C3D8R). For these models, components were considered elastic. Material data for the aluminium was from [32], steel data was from [33] and for the CFRP from [34]. Table 1 shows the change in peak stress for an array of micropins compared to a single fastener with an equivalent area. These results show a decrease in peak stress. The results also show a further decrease in peak stress with the addition of an interference fit pin. These results support micropins as a viable method for decreasing the effect of the geometric stress raiser inherent in mechanically fastened joints.

Sample compared equivalent single fastener	Change in peak stress
Aluminium with the fastener hole only	+0.5%
Aluminium with interference fit pin	-15%
CFRP with the fastener hole only	-6%
CFRP with interference fit pin	-38%

Table 1: Change in peak stresses for single fasteners vs equivalent area micropins

4 INSERTION TESTING

Initial testing investigated the load required to insert the steel micropin through the drilled hole in the composite-to-aluminium joint. The load-displacement response was recorded by gripping the pin in an Instron 4465 load frame and supporting the sample while the pin was pulled through. Figure 2 shows the load-displacement response during pin insertion. Initially, the pin deforms elastically until it reaches the limit of static friction, then the pin is pulled through. The load to pull the pin through decreases very slightly with increasing displacement. This small reduction is due to the wear in the composite and metal. These results can be used to define the mode I response of a single pin and hence the surface traction.

Figure 2: Pin insertion test results.

5 SINGLE PIN LAP SHEAR TESTS

Tests were carried out on a single pin under lap shear loading. Four samples were tested under tension in an Instron 4465 load frame using a 250 N load cell. Figure 3 shows the lap shear response and Table 2 gives the bearing properties. The results show a consistent ultimate load and maximum bearing stress for samples 1, 3 and 4. Sample 2 has a 9% greater than average ultimate load and bearing stress. Bearing stiffness is consistent for samples 2, 3 and 4, but lower for sample 1.

Figure 3: Lap shear response of single pin joints

	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4
Ultimate bearing load (N)	57.5	61.6	55.1	55.6
Max bearing Stress (MPa)	79.9	85.6	76.5	77.2
Bearing Stiffness (GPa)	0.75	1.01	1.00	0.97
Yield Stress (MPa)	62.7	67.9	69.8	67.0

Table 2: Bearing properties of single pin joints

The joint exhibits an elastic-plastic response to lap shear loading, with maximum load occurring at a displacement of ~ 0.2 mm. This result shows that the maximum load occurs after the pin is partially pulled-out, and hence has a reduced contact surface area. Ultimate loading occurring with a reduced surface area suggests that the pin-CFRP and pin-aluminium interface experiences enhanced friction through snubbing. The image of the failed pin shown in Figure 4 and the snubbing effects observed in similar systems observed by Cox [35] support this conclusion. Strain hardening of the steel pin may also lead to the ultimate load occurring once the pin has started pulling-out and plastic bending has occurred in the pin.

After exceeding the ultimate load, there is significant variation in the load-displacement profile. Sample 1 shows the pin maintained a relatively high but progressively decreasing load as it pulls-out from the CFRP until it reaches 0.88 mm. At this displacement, the entire length of the pin has completely pulled-out of the CFRP sheet. The linear response suggests that as the pin pulls-out, the load decreased linearly with the decreasing contact surface area. Samples 2 and 4 show a similar decrease; however the ultimate failure occurs at a smaller displacement. Failure before the entire length of the pin has pulled-out suggests that damage to the CFRP has allowed the hole to become large enough for the pin to pull directly out of the bottom-most ply of the composite. Figure 5 shows the enlarged hole in the CFRP substrate after the pin has pulled-out which would have allowed for the pin to be released before the entire length was pulled-out. Sample 3 fails rapidly after approximately 0.2 mm displacement with the "bump" in the load-displacement curve due to end of the pin coming

into contact with the middle 0° plys. These variations occur after the ultimate load has been reached with continuing displacement beyond both the yield limit and ultimate bearing strength of the joint.

Images of the failed sample have been taken and used to aid interpretation of the failure mechanisms. Figure 4 shows the pin after failure. There is plastic bending in the pin immediately above the aluminium sheet. The plastic bending observed suggests some strain hardening occurred. Burring and deformation can also be observed in the aluminium sheet at the bottom of the pin, suggesting that snubbing also occurred. Figure 5 shows the hole in the CFRP after failure, with fibre damage in the load bearing direction. The fibre damage enlarged the hole, eventually decreasing the traction force due to the interference decreasing. This damage also suggests that snubbing occurred.

Figure 4: Microscope image of pin and aluminium sheet post failure showing the bending in the pin and burring in the aluminium sheet.

Figure 5: Microscope image of CFRP hole post failure showing fibre damage in the loading direction

6 MULTI-PIN LAP SHEAR TESTS

Lap shear tests on a multi-pin lap joint were carried out to investigate the load-displacement response and the failure mechanism. A 3 x 3 array square array of interference fit pins was manufactured with a spacing of 5 mm over a joint area of 100 mm². Five samples were tested under tension in an Instron 4465 load frame using a 50 kN load cell. Figure 6 shows the load-displacement

response of the joints. The joints follow an elastic response up until 0.1 mm displacement. The joints then deform plastically before reaching their ultimate load between 0.3 mm and 0.7 mm. Despite the different displacement to failure, the ultimate load is consistent. Once reaching the ultimate load, the pins pull-out of the CFRP sheet and the load carried by the joint decreases suddenly. As with the single pin joints, the multi-pin joint also exhibits an elastic-plastic response. The maximum load occurs after the pins have started pulling-out. The delay again suggests that enhanced friction through snubbing is occurring as well as some strain hardening in the pins.

Figure 6: Multipin lap shear test load-displacement response

Sample	1	2	3	4	5
Ultimate bearing load (N)	827	865	886	892	896
Max bearing Stress (MPa)	115	120	123	124	124
Bearing Stiffness (GPa)	0.81	0.78	0.76	0.73	0.81
Yield Stress (MPa)	81.7	98.3	93.5	95.9	71.5

Table 3: Bearing properties of multipin joints

Table 3 shows the bearing properties of the multi-pin joint samples. The ultimate load and maximum bearing stress vary from the mean by less than 6% for all the samples. The bearing stiffness varies from 0.73 GPa to 0.81 GPa, a difference of 10%. The 2% offset yield stress, however, does vary considerably with the lowest value being 71.5 MPa and the highest being 98.3 MPa.

When compared to a single pin joint, the total ultimate bearing load for nine pins is greater than nine times the ultimate bearing load for a single pin. A corresponding improvement in the maximum bearing stress was also observed. The average bearing load is 97.0 N per pin, whereas the average bearing load from the single pin experiments was 57.5 N per pin. The yield stress of the joint has increased from an average of 66.9 MPa for a single pin joint to an average of 88.16 MPa for a nine pin joint. The bearing stiffness, however, has decreased from an average of 0.93 GPa for the single pin joint to 0.78 GPa for the multipin joint.

7 SINGLE PIN MODEL

A numerical model has been developed to investigate the stress state during lap shear loading. The model used an elastoplastic model for the aluminium and steel pin. The aluminium was modelled using the Johnson-Cook plasticity model [36] and data from [32]. The steel pin was modelled using properties for ASTM A227 steel wire assuming linear strain hardening [37]. Table 4 and Table 5 give the material parameters.

Material	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Poisson's Ratio	A (MPa)	B (MPa)	n	m
Aluminum	67	0.33	262	1621	0.2783	1.34

Table 4: Material properties of AA6061-T6

Material	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Poisson's Ratio	Per cent Elongation at Failure	Yield Stress (MPa)	UTS (MPa)
ASTM A227 Steel	190	0.29	12	1430	1720

Table 5: Material properties of ASTM A227 steel wire.

A variety of models exist for damage and post-failure behaviour of composites under impact and penetration. Review by [38] of many models for composite failure suggested using the Puck criteria for fibre and matrix failure [39]. Once meeting the failure conditions, further evolution of the stress state depends on a modified stiffness matrix. These models use the approach suggested by [40]. Element deletion occurs once fibre tension or fibre compression failure occurred. Once matrix failure occurred, the stiffness matrix was modified. Table 6 shows the modifications to the stiffness post matrix failure. This approach is implemented on an element-by-element basis using Abaqus Explicit 6.14 with a user subroutine (VUSDFLD). The interlaminar response of the composite was modelled using cohesive surfaces. The model uses material properties from [34]. Combining the Puck criteria for failure and the Carmano and Matthews post-failure allows modelling of the composite through the entire process of interference fit and composite damage due to the lap shear load.

Failure mode	Partially reduced stiffnesses
Matrix tensile failure	$E_{22} = 0.2E_{22}, G_{12} = 0.2 G_{12}, G_{23} = 0.2G_{23}$
Matrix compressive failure	$E_{22} = 0.4E_{22}, G_{12} = 0.4 G_{12}, G_{23} = 0.4G_{23}$

Table 6: Material stiffness degradation coefficients for the CFRP laminate.

The FE model used a single explicit step to replicate the lap shear response. The mesh was refined to 0.1 mm elements near the pin-substrate interface and a global size of 10 mm away from the edge to reduce computational time. The model of the single pin lap shear test used a total of 65852 elements. Initially, the assembly had an overclosure between the pin and the substrates. This overclosure was resolved in the first increment of the explicit solution, defining the interference fit. The step time was chosen to be 0.1 s, and mass scaling was used to optimise the accuracy of the solution while minimising computational time. Automatic mass scaling aiming for a time step of 1×10^{-8} s was found to be a reasonable balance. Friction coefficients for the interfaces were found in the literature;

the aluminium-to-CFRP interface used a static friction coefficient of 0.23 [41]. As there is minimal load across this interface, varying the coefficient of friction of the aluminium-to-CFRP interface had a negligible effect on the numerical accuracy of the model. Previous work on interference fit bolting [12] suggested a coefficient of friction for steel-to-CFRP of 0.1-0.2. Varying this value was found to affect the ultimate load and the fracture energy of the model. A parametric study suggested that a coefficient of friction of 0.15 was the best fit to the data as a whole, however different coefficients of friction were a better fit for individual samples. [42] suggests a coefficient of friction of 0.61 for the steel to aluminium interface. As the aluminium-to-steel contact area is much larger than the steel to CFRP contact area, reasonable variations in this value, have little effect on the accuracy of the model. A half symmetry was used to reduce the total number of elements required. The model used 3D (hexahedral) elements with reduced integration to balance the computational expense and accuracy.

Figure 7: Comparison of the model prediction of the single pin response with experimental results.

Figure 7 compares the modelled load-displacement curve with the experimental results. The model can predict the ultimate load, stiffness and displacement to the ultimate load. It is also able to replicate the elastic-plastic response of the joint. The displacement to ultimate failure varies depending on subtle changes in the coefficient of friction between the pin and the CFRP sheet. The displacement will also be affected by variations in the coefficient of friction through-the-thickness of the panel and on different orientations of the plies. As the model uses meso-mechanical models for the composite, these intra-ply effects were not included.

Figure 8 **Error! Reference source not found.** shows the cross-section of the progressive joint failure under lap shear loading. Figure 8a shows the stress state in the pin and composite after resolving the interference fit. The stress state shows the increased stresses in the middle two 0° plies. **Error! Reference source not found.** Figure 8b shows the pin during lap shear loading. The pin bends plastically due to the loading. An increase in the stress is observed at the point of contact of the pin on the surface of the CFRP and aluminium. The increase in stress shows a higher surface load and hence enhanced friction. Figure 8c **Error! Reference source not found.** shows the failure of the joint when the pin has overcome the friction of the CFRP hole and finally pulls-out of the hole due to secondary bending of the CFRP sheet caused by the eccentricity in the load. The model assumes this will occur based only on the pressure and friction. In the experiment, there will be variations in surface roughness, leading to some snagging in the hole and a longer displacement to failure.

a)

b)

c)

Figure 8: The progress of loading a single pin to failure. a) the initial stress state, b) pin during loading showing snubbing and bending, c) the ultimate failure of the pin.

8 MULTI-PIN MODEL

The 3 x 3 pin multi-pin joint was modelled numerically using the same material parameters and model inputs as the single pin joint. In this case, the half-symmetry means that three full pins and three half-pins were used to model the joint. In order to get a satisfactory mesh while balancing computational time, some changes were made to the mesh compared to the single pin model. The pin-substrate interface was changed to have 0.1 mm elements for a region 1 mm around the interface between the pin and the substrate. A further rectangle extending 5 mm beyond the pins used 0.25 mm elements. The aluminium sheet had eight elements through-the-thickness. Each ply of the CFRP had two elements through-the-thickness. Again the mesh sizing away from the region of interest was increased to 10 mm. The total number of elements in the FE model was 74896. A mesh convergence study was carried out to confirm the validity of this mesh. This study investigated the effect of the number of elements in the immediate area surrounding the pins, the number of elements through the thickness of each CFRP ply and the number of elements through the thickness of the AA6061-T6 substrate. The results are shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** These results suggest the mesh is valid for this model

Elements through CFRP ply thickness	Elements through AA thickness	Element size surrounding pins (m)	Maximum load (N)
1	8	0.0001	646
2	8	0.0001	885
3	8	0.0001	881
2	8	0.0002	928
2	16	0.0001	910

Table 7: Results of mesh convergence study

Figure 9 shows a comparison between the modelled load-displacement curve for the multi-pin joint and the experimental results. The model can replicate the stiffness, ultimate load and displacement-to-failure. It is also able to replicate the elastic-plastic response of the joint. As with the single pin joint model, the coefficient of friction between the steel pin and the CFRP sheets can be varied to match individual samples better.

Figure 9: Model of the load-displacement response of the multi-pin sample compared to the experimental data

Error! Reference source not found. shows the progressive failure of the joint. As with the single pin model, **Error! Reference source not found.** shows the stresses induced by the interference fit. Again higher stress are found in the 0° plys which have a higher stiffness in the cross-sectioned plane. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows the bending and snubbing of the pins as the load was applied. A peak in the stress can be seen at the base of the CFRP sheet. This peak corresponds to a higher normal force and hence a greater frictional force acting against the pull-out of the pins. Figure 10c shows failure as the pins pull-out due to secondary bending induced by the eccentricity in the load.

Figure 10: The progress of loading a multi-pin joint to failure and highlighting individual pins. a) initial stress state, b) pin during loading showing snubbing and bending and c) final failure showing the pins pulling out of the CFRP sheet.

9 CONCLUSION

Interference fit micropinned joints have been developed and characterised under lap shear loading. Joints were manufactured from aluminium alloys and CFRP laminates reinforced in through-thickness direction using steel pins. The results showed a decrease in the peak stress around the holes in a multi-pin joint compared to an equivalent single fastener.

Joints bridged by a single pin were manufactured to attain an understanding of the response to lap shear loading. The joint studied showed an elastic-plastic response to lap shear loading with ultimate load occurring once the pin was partially pulled-out. The delay suggests that snubbing and plastic hardening of the pin have some effect on the response of the joint. Finite element analysis was able to model this response, supporting the theory of snubbing and plastic hardening of the pins. The joints ultimately failed due to the pin pulling-out of the CFRP sheet after secondary bending occurred due to the eccentricity in the load.

Multi-pin joints were manufactured using a 3×3 square array of pins. The joints studied also showed an elastic-plastic response to lap shear loading with the ultimate load occurring once the pins were partially pulled-out. The load-to-failure for nine pins was more than nine times the load to failure for a single pin joint. A corresponding increase in the ultimate bearing stress and yield stress was measured, although the bearing stiffness was reduced. Numerical modelling was able to replicate the failure mode, ultimate load and displacement-to-failure.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to acknowledge the financial support of the ARC Training Centre for Lightweight Automotive Structures and the Australian Research Council (Grant Reference IC160100032)

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Gibbs, W. Joost, and C. Schutte, *Workshop Report: Lightweight Vehicle Technical Requirements and Gaps for Lightweight Propulsion and Materials*. 2013.
- [2] A. Pramanik, A.K. Basak, Y. Dong, P.K. Sarker, M.S. Uddin, G. Littlefair, A.R. Dixit, and S. Chattopadhyaya, Joining of carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites and aluminium alloys – A review, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*. **101**, 2017. pp. 1-29 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2017.06.007>).
- [3] N. Chowdhury, W.K. Chiu, J. Wang, and P. Chang, Static and fatigue testing thin riveted, bonded and hybrid carbon fiber double lap joints used in aircraft structures, *Composite Structures*. **121**, 2015. pp. 315-323 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2014.11.004>).
- [4] A.T.T. Nguyen, C.K. Amarasinghe, M. Brandt, S. Feih, and A.C. Orifici, Loading, support and geometry effects for pin-reinforced hybrid metal-composite joints, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*. **98**, 2017. pp. 192-206 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2017.03.019>).
- [5] J. Jiang and Y. Bi, Effect of parameters on local stress field in single-lap bolted joints with the interference fit, *Advances in Mechanical Engineering*. **8**, 2016. pp. 1687814016647255 (doi: 10.1177/1687814016647255).
- [6] Y. Zhou, H.Y. Nezhad, C. Hou, X. Wan, C. McCarthy, and M. McCarthy, A three dimensional implicit finite element damage model and its application to single-lap multi-bolt composite joints with variable clearance, *Composite Structures*. **131**, 2015. pp. 1060-1072).
- [7] S.-Y. Kim, B. He, D. Kim, C.S. Shim, and H.C. Song, Bearing strength of interference-fit pin joined glass fiber reinforced plastic composites, *Journal of Composite Materials*. **0**, 2016. pp. 0021998316636462 (doi: 10.1177/0021998316636462).

- [8] D. Song, Y. Li, K. Zhang, P. Liu, H. Cheng, and T. Wu, Stress distribution modeling for interference-fit area of each individual layer around composite laminates joint, *Composites Part B: Engineering*. **78**, 2015. pp. 469-479 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2015.04.013>).
- [9] D. Song, K. Zhang, Y. Li, P. Liu, X. Yan, and W. Su, Effect of interference percentage on damage mechanism of carbon fiber reinforced plastics laminate during interference-fit bolt installation, *Journal of Composite Materials*. **51**, 2016. pp. 1031-1043 (doi: 10.1177/0021998316658538).
- [10] J. Hu, K. Zhang, Q. Yang, H. Cheng, P. Liu, and Y. Yang, An experimental study on mechanical response of single-lap bolted CFRP composite interference-fit joints, *Composite Structures*. **196**, 2018. pp. 76-88 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2018.05.016>).
- [11] S.-Y. Kim, B. He, and C.-S. Shim, An experimental and numerical study on the interference-fit pin installation process for cross-ply glass fiber reinforced plastics (GFRP), *Composites Part B: Engineering*. **54**, 2013. pp. 153-162).
- [12] P. Zou, K. Zhang, Y. Li, P. Liu, and H. Xie, Bearing strength and failure analysis on the interference-fit double shear-lap pin-loaded composite, *International Journal of Damage Mechanics*. **27**, 2016. pp. 179-200 (doi: 10.1177/1056789516671774).
- [13] A.A. Pisano, P. Fuschi, and D. De Domenico, Failure modes prediction of multi-pin joints FRP laminates by limit analysis, *Composites Part B: Engineering*. **46**, 2013. pp. 197-206 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2012.09.071>).
- [14] K. Xue, Progressive Analysis of Bearing Failure in Pin-Loaded Composite Laminates Using an Elasto-Plastic Damage Model, *Materials Sciences and Applications*. **9**, 2018. pp. 576).
- [15] F.X. Irisarri, F. Laurin, and N. Carrere, 6 - Strength prediction of bolted joints in carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites, in *Composite Joints and Connections*. 2011, Woodhead Publishing. p. 208-244.
- [16] A.P. Mouritz, Review of z-pinned composite laminates, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*. **38**, 2007. pp. 2383-2397 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2007.08.016>).
- [17] B.N. Cox, Mechanisms and models for delamination in the presence of through-thickness reinforcement, *Adv Compos Lett*. **8**, 1999. pp. 249-56).
- [18] B. Cox and N. Sridhar, A traction law for inclined fiber tows bridging mixed-mode cracks, *Mechanics of Advanced Materials and Structures*. **9**, 2002. pp. 299-331).
- [19] D.D. Cartié, B. Cox, and N. Fleck, Mechanisms of crack bridging by composite and metallic rods, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*. **35**, 2004. pp. 1325-1336).
- [20] M. Grassi and X. Zhang, Finite element analyses of mode I interlaminar delamination in z-fibre reinforced composite laminates, *Composites Science and Technology*. **63**, 2003. pp. 1815-1832 (doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0266-3538\(03\)00134-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0266-3538(03)00134-9)).
- [21] D.D.R. Cartié, G. Dell'Anno, E. Poulin, and I.K. Partridge, 3D reinforcement of stiffener-to-skin T-joints by Z-pinning and tufting, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*. **73**, 2006. pp. 2532-2540 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfracmech.2006.06.012>).
- [22] M. Grassi, B. Cox, and X. Zhang, Simulation of pin-reinforced single-lap composite joints, *Composites Science and Technology*. **66**, 2006. pp. 1623-1638 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2005.11.013>).
- [23] T.M. Koh, S. Feih, and A.P. Mouritz, Strengthening mechanics of thin and thick composite T-joints reinforced with z-pins, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*. **43**, 2012. pp. 1308-1317 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2012.03.023>).
- [24] Y.-B. Park, B.-H. Lee, J.-H. Kweon, J.-H. Choi, and I.-H. Choi, The strength of composite bonded T-joints transversely reinforced by carbon pins, *Composite Structures*. **94**, 2012. pp. 625-634 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2011.08.026>).

- [25] J. Toral Vazquez, B. Castanié, J.-J. Barrau, and N. Swiergiel, Multi-level analysis of low-cost Z-pinned composite joints: Part 2: Joint behaviour, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*. **42**, 2011. pp. 2082-2092 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2011.09.017>).
- [26] K.L. Rugg, B.N. Cox, and R. Massabò, Mixed mode delamination of polymer composite laminates reinforced through the thickness by z-fibers, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*. **33**, 2002. pp. 177-190 (doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-835X\(01\)00109-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1359-835X(01)00109-9)).
- [27] W. Yan, H.-Y. Liu, and Y.-W. Mai, Mode II delamination toughness of z-pinned laminates, *Composites Science and Technology*. **64**, 2004. pp. 1937-1945 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2004.02.008>).
- [28] P. Chang, A.P. Mouritz, and B.N. Cox, Properties and failure mechanisms of pinned composite lap joints in monotonic and cyclic tension, *Composites Science and Technology*. **66**, 2006. pp. 2163-2176 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2005.11.039>).
- [29] S. Ucsnik, M. Scheerer, S. Zaremba, and D.H. Pahr, Experimental investigation of a novel hybrid metal-composite joining technology, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*. **41**, 2010. pp. 369-374 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2009.11.003>).
- [30] A.T.T. Nguyen, M. Brandt, S. Feih, and A.C. Orifici, Pin pull-out behaviour for hybrid metal-composite joints with integrated reinforcements, *Composite Structures*. **155**, 2016. pp. 160-172 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2016.07.047>).
- [31] ASTM, *D5961 / D5961M-17, Standard Test Method for Bearing Response of Polymer Matrix Composite Laminates*. 2017, ASTM International: West Conshohocken, PA.,
- [32] Dassault Systems, *Simulation of the ballistic performance of aluminium plates with Abaqus Explicit*, in *Abaqus Technology Brief*, Simulia, Editor. 2012.
- [33] Z. Kennan, *Determination of the Constitutive Equations for 1080 Steel and Vascomax 300*, in *Engineering and Management*. 2005, Air University.
- [34] J. Ahamed, M. Joosten, P. Callus, S. John, and C.H. Wang, Ply-interleaving technique for joining hybrid carbon/glass fibre composite materials, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*. **84**, 2016. pp. 134-146).
- [35] B. Cox, Snubbing effects in the pullout of a fibrous rod from a laminate, *Mechanics of Advanced Materials and Structures*. **12**, 2005. pp. 85-98).
- [36] G.R. Johnson and W.H. Cook, Fracture characteristics of three metals subjected to various strains, strain rates, temperatures and pressures, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*. **21**, 1985. pp. 31-48 (doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0013-7944\(85\)90052-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/0013-7944(85)90052-9)).
- [37] ASTM International, *Standard Specification for Steel Wire, Cold-Drawn for Mechanical Springs*. 2017: West Conshohocken, PA.
- [38] A.-S. Kaddour and M. Hinton, Maturity of 3D failure criteria for fibre-reinforced composites: Comparison between theories and experiments: Part B of WWFE-II, *Journal of Composite materials*. **47**, 2013. pp. 925-966).
- [39] A. Puck and H. Schürmann, Failure analysis of FRP laminates by means of physically based phenomenological models, *Composites Science and Technology*. **62**, 2002. pp. 1633-1662).
- [40] P.P. Camanho and F. Matthews, A progressive damage model for mechanically fastened joints in composite laminates, *Journal of composite materials*. **33**, 1999. pp. 2248-2280).
- [41] J. Schön, Coefficient of friction for aluminum in contact with a carbon fiber epoxy composite, *Tribology International*. **37**, 2004. pp. 395-404 (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.triboint.2003.11.008>).
- [42] Engineering ToolBox. *Friction and Friction Coefficients*. 2004 1/May/2018; Available from: https://www.engineeringtoolbox.com/friction-coefficients-d_778.html.